

COATING SOLUTIONS FOR WAFERLEVEL OPTICS

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ABSTRACT

In a trend to reduce manufacturing cost, optical components are increasingly manufactured on wafer level. In our presentation we will show how this concept applies to smart glasses and edge emitting lasers. Both applications require optical thin film coating steps to enable their function. The presentation will address the special requirements such as excellent edge coverage and high thickness accuracy. In order to meet these challenges, we developed coating systems which combine the strength of semiconductor machines in terms of automated handling with the accuracy of optical coating machines.

KEYWORDS: thin film coating, optical interference coating, coating equipment

INTRODUCTION

Optical components for consumer applications today are very often manufactured on glass wafers rather than on smaller individual substrates. A good example of this are smart glasses for Augmented Reality (AR) and Mixed Reality (MR). These applications are expected to reach mass market in the near future.

In smart glasses, the lens has novel functions. The projected image is coupled into the glass by a grating coupler. Within the glass the light is waveguided to the region where it is coupled out towards the eye by using a second grating or a dielectric beam splitter. The outcoupling region is at the same time used for vision, thus the grating or beam splitter has to be highly transparent. The elements on the lens require various coatings, which are manufactured on wafer level. The lenses will be machined into single elements at a late stage in the processing chain. We will show how manufacturing of these elements benefits from a coating machine combining the strengths of semiconductor and optics deposition systems.

A second example will show how the facets of edge emitting lasers can be coated. Traditionally, after epitaxy the lasers are diced and put into jigs, such that the facets face the coating beam. In the newly developed process however, the individual lasers can be coated while still being on the epitaxy wafer. The process is optimized such that a high quality mirror or an antireflex coating is obtained on the side wall facet.

EXPERIMENTAL

The deposition systems used for the development of the processes in the examples are the Evatec Clusterline CLN200 BPM and CLN300 magnetron sputter deposition systems. Most important for applications on wafer level is automatic substrate handling – a feature, which is standard in semiconductor applications, but is not widespread for optical coatings. The CLN300 is a cluster tool with a maximum of 6 individual sputter stations for coating wafers of 300mm diameter (Figure 1a). It is very well suited for coatings with only a few layers. The BPM tool on the other hand is a system with a turntable configuration and a maximum of 4 magnetron sputter sources (Figure 1b). The substrates of a maximum diameter of 200mm get exposed to the active source repeatedly such that optical interference coating stacks with a high number of alternating layers of materials with high and low refractive index can be formed. The accuracy of film thickness in such high layer count filters is key and therefore these systems are equipped with in-situ process control such as optical monitoring for film thickness termination and plasma emission monitoring for high and stable deposition rates of fully oxidized films. Furthermore, an optional plasma source can be used to influence layer properties such as stress or surface roughness.

Figure 1: (a) CLN300 cluster tool equipped with 5 individual process chambers, (b) opened BPM magnetron sputter system with turntable configuration and 4 sputter sources.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As discussed in the introduction, gratings are used in augmented reality applications to couple light into the waveguide, which is formed by a high refractive index glass used as the lens of the spectacles. The input grating needs to be coated with aluminum in order to enhance coupling efficiency, with a key requirement being a very good side wall coverage. Side wall coverage is a well-known requirement for coatings in semiconductor industry, thus, the process development for vias could be transferred to optical gratings. Figure 2a shows a Focused Ion Beam (FIB) cross section of an in-coupling grating coated with aluminum. This coating was manufactured on a 300mm substrate using the CLN 300 deposition tool. As can be seen, the side walls and bottom of the grating are homogeneously coated.

Figure 2: (a) Focused Ion Beam (FIB) cross section of an aluminum coated coupling grating with good side wall coverage, (b) 10 layer antireflection coating for angular range 0-45° deg on high index glass ($n=2$).

The grating is used from the glass side. Thus, the entrance surface of the high refractive index glass forming the lens has to be coated with an antireflection coating. Depending on the specific architecture of the smart glass, the antireflection coating will be required to work at a high angle of incidence and over a large angular range. Such antireflection coatings are best deposited in a deposition tool such as the BPM, which is optimized for optical applications with optical monitoring for accurate layer termination and plasma emission monitoring in order to be able to deposit a fully oxidized dielectric layer at a high deposition rate. By doing so, the designed reflection curve can closely be matched, as can be seen in Figure 2b.

Figure 3: (a) Traditional method for coating edge emitting lasers in a jig holding diced laser bars. (b) Advanced method coating lasers directly on wafer. (c) the FIB cross section shows the homogeneous mirror coating on laser facet (within red circles)

The second example shown is the coating of the facet of an edge emitting laser with a mirror coating. Traditionally, after epitaxy the wafers are diced into laser bars and put into jigs for coating as seen in Fig. 3a. In the newly developed process however, the lasers are coated on the epitaxy wafer. The process is optimized such that it results in just the correct thickness to form a mirror or antireflection coating on the side wall facet. Figure 3c shows a cross section of the facet of a laser coated on the epitaxy wafer. The coating is dense and very even in thickness. The area denoted with W is tungsten, which was needed for sample preparation.

CONCLUSIONS

In the paper we did show how manufacturing of optical devices on wafer level can benefit from coating machines combining strengths established in fr semiconductor and optical manufacturing.

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